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A Fight for a Better Life

In a small shanty, they called home
Lived a little boy celled in a room
Fed so little by his mother at noon
And abused by everyone at dawn

Every action against him brings pain
But he owns it as his sin
Keeping smiles even if he is chained
Physical, emotional and sexual abused keep him in vain

When his body cannot endure
He closed his eyes for all the torture
Wishing that this will end soon
And his soul will be at peace for sure

But God has a different plan for him to fly
When he opens his eyes, he sees a clear sky
A bit of hope reflects on his cry
A freedom he owes in every sigh

A lady in red was in sight
Looking at him with a smile so bright
She became her hero with so much might
And give him a dream to fight

And now, that little boy is already a man
Doing everything that he can
Promised to be a law enforcer as long as he can
And prevent the criminal act of every lawless man.